

Time In The Qur'an And Its Link To The Ecosystem

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 02, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 25, 2020</p> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Quran Time Ecosystem</p>	<p>The time in the quran is not only related to the natural environment, but also to human activities. The environment has implications for a wide range of ecosystem services, including water quality, nutrient cycle, soil conservation and carbon sequestration. Conservation of environmental biodiversity. , Works to preserve the ecosystems that affect the continuity of life and understanding the contribution that the book of God is working on the basic components of the natural and human environment by controlling the side effects of human activities, and to achieve this we must find the link to the environmental aspects of time, In Quran, which refers to the relationship between environment, time and human behavior, and the correlation of these three variables in identifying the main risks that lead to the erosion and decay of life over time, and the importance of the temporal factor in Quran in the analysis and understanding of the future environment Natural and human, the tastiest contribute positively to be in determining the time periods of environmental and human link between them and the environment of mutual relationship and the activities of activities, and this in turn has the importance of environmental management systems at the global level .</p>

Introduction

The Islamic religion was concerned with the factor of time through its holy book, the Noble Qur'an, and found a difference between the divine and human time experienced by humans, and since the Qur'an defined this separation between the two. Times, we can calculate the human discoveries of the world, between human life in divine existence, the time we take as servants, and how much is the actual life of human beings. All of this made us think about worldly life and ALLAH response to our demands.

Chapter one

Temporal and spatial dimension in the Holy Quran

In the Qur'an, he describes the time when it is almost in all the noble verses, but we will discuss anyone in which time was mentioned in a distinctive way (وَإِنِّيَوْمًا عَنَدَ رَبِّكَ أَفْسَنَةٌ مِّمَّا تَعُدُّونَ) Hence, the Qur'anic miracle is clear to describe the Creator, the Exalted, the Majestic, continuous sidereal time , and before beginning to explain this verse scientifically, we must pass quickly to the most important logical linguistic interpretations, the first of which is the interpretation of al-Tabari (ALLAH Almighty mentioned): And hurry to you, O Muhammad, your polytheists, with what you consider from the torment of ALLAH to their polytheism and their denial of you in what you brought with him from God in the world, and he will not succeed ALLAH promised him that He promised you that He would inflict torment and revenge them on the urgent world. He did that, and he fulfilled them with what He promised them, and He killed them on the day of Badr, and the people of interpretation differed on the day when most of His praise said Some of them: It is one of the days when ALLAH created the heavens and the earth.

Al-Saadi's interpretation (i.e., those lied to you are rushed by torture, because of their ignorance, injustice, stubbornness, incapacity to God, and disbelief to His messengers, and ALLAH will not break His promise. To you, O Muhammad, their wheel will not provoke you and make them incapable of us. For in front of them is the Day of Resurrection, in which the first and the last of them gather together, and they are permitted to do their deeds, and the painful permanent suffering falls on them. Whether they are tormented in this world or torment is late for them, then this day must be a hand, Khayyam. *ولو أنا لله ليم، ولو* Hurry the torment, because a day with him is like a thousand years of what you count .

After reviewing ancient and modern interpretations, there is a scientific vision of ALLAH Almighty's saying that it is a timescale that cannot be ignored because it refers to a very fast time. , The luminous year symbolized by it. This sign denotes very large distances, such as the distance between the Earth and other sky bodies. The speed of light is 300 / thousand / sec. With this speed, light travels 18 million kilometers per minute. This is called the light minute. The distance covered by light in one year is 9,460,730,472,580,800 meters, i.e. it is 9.461 trillion km, i.e. it travels at a speed of 299.792.458 m/s (See Figure 1) .

Figure 1. A map showing the stars 12.5 light-years from the sun (Seidemann , 1992)

The spin mechanism of celestial bodies, the size of distances, and their accuracy depend on important constants of cosmic time such as the apparent solar motion that is not uniform and the length of the solar day is not constant throughout the year. The difference between the apparent solar time and the (normal) solar time is called the equation of time. Two known features of our solar system lie on the basis of periodic irregularities in solar motion. As the Earth's angular velocity relative to the sun varies periodically throughout the year. The plane tilts from Earth's orbit in relation to the tropics. Therefore, the angular velocity of the relative motion of the eclipse must be projected at the equatorial level before being incorporated into the measurement of time. This mathematical expression of the projection factor of angular velocities results in a swing function with two periods of the year. The difference between the maximum values of the time equation is approximately half an hour. The time equation response for parameter variation is analyzed Main. In order to visualize the factors that contribute to the equation of time, and that the Almighty Creator granted this mechanism ultimate precision as it reaches (10123), which is a precision that cannot be reached humanly. Earth's shadow extends 1.5 million km to space. The Moon orbits approximately 384,000 km so that it can pass through the Earth's shadow. The Earth's shadow consists of shadow and semi-shadow. This leads to three possible types of eclipses.

And when comparing the time of God with the measured time, it means the distance that light travels in a year with the timing of God, which is multiplied by 1000, where $9,460,730,472,580,800 * 1000 = 9,460,730,472,580,800,000$ m , and when converting it to km (19460730472580800) km

This number and what the Holy Qur'an refers to did not reach the knowledge of man to its meaning, as the Qur'an is ahead of its time, that the maximum extent reached by a person from a distance is 800 million kilometers from the ground, and this means that the distance that he discovered in space reaches 24.32 km in space This means that there is 75.68% of the space that humans have not reached.

Chapter two

Earth's changing angular velocity algorithm to move the universe.

Kepler's laws test Kepler's first law applies to all planets that move in elliptical orbits around the sun, where the latter is placed in one of two coordination points. Kepler's second law - the so-called law of regions - describes the speed of planets. The area swept at each fixed interval ($= da / dt$). Thus, during the time period t , the radius from the sun cuts to the Earth an area.

(b, a-axis ellipse, T - duration of time). Let us now conclude the Earth's angular velocity as a function of time. The angle the Earth covers after leaving the galaxy is called "true differences", and here indicated by the symbol R (see Figure 1). Let's imagine "middle ground" that also has a time factor T.

Figure 2. The R, M and E angles at a specified point in time. The attribute factor between the elliptical orbit and the circle that runs through the perigee and apogee is given by b / a . Since the angular velocity of "real earth" and "middle earth" is both constant, the ratio between the two agreed regions is the same between the regions of the circle and the ellipse, i.e., $1: b / a$.

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A constant velocity operates in a circular orbit and the sun is at its center. This "middle ground" covers an angle called "mean difference" (M), in the same time period that the real earth covers the angle R. In Fig. 1, where M is withdrawn from the center of the ellipse. The orbit of the "middle earth" is the circle during the decrease and apogee. The “middle earth” begins to decline at the same time that the earth begins to spin real. Since the angular velocity of "middle earth" is constant and its eruption lasts one year (T), simple equations are the simple equation

$$M = 2\pi \frac{t}{T},$$

Where t is the time period for the passage of time. It is very useful to define a third angle as a link between M and R (see Figure 1). Where the vertical circle derived from the position of the real earth (E) crosses on the main axis, the circle, which is the "middle earth" orbit, at point A. The angle is called PZA and here we find a strange contras.

Chapter Three : The Ecosystem In The Qur'an.

Natural factors such as (water and soil) are considered important and basic factors in preserving the biological diversity of the environment, and evidence of that is the Almighty saying in the name of ALLAH, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful.

وَمِنْ آيَاتِهِ أَنْتَرَى الْأَرْضَ خَاشِعَةً فَإِذَا أَنْزَلْنَا عَلَيْهَا الْمَاءَ اهْتَزَّتْ وَرَبَتْ ^٤ إِنَّ الَّذِي أَحْيَاهَا لَمُحْيِي الْمَوْتَى ^٥ إِنَّهُ عَلَىٰ كُلِّ شَيْءٍ قَدِيرٌ

(Surat FOSELT : 39)

{ وَمِنْ آيَاتِهِ } Evidence of the perfection of his ability, his uniqueness in king, measure and oneness { وَرَبَّتْ } That is: it moved the plant { وَرَبَّتْ } . { اهْتَزَّتْ } That is: rain { فَإِذَا أَنْزَلْنَا عَلَيْهَا الْمَاءَ } That is: there is no plant in it { أَنْتَرَى الْأَرْضَ خَاشِعَةً } .

Then: I grew from each joyful husband, so the servants and the country would greet him { إِنَّ الَّذِي أَحْيَاهَا } After her death and inertia, { لَمُحْيِي الْمَوْتَى } From their graves to the day of their resurrection, and their publication {for He is

able to do all things.} Just as his ability to revive the earth was not beyond her death, she cannot resurrect the dead .

From here, ALLAH shows the importance of water in the environment, which is the basis for life and change of the earth's cover. Then, the Mighty, the Mighty, linked the life cycle to the life of the earth, and here is a clear and explicit indication that death helps in the life cycle in nature, so it is a mutual relationship between decomposition and the fertility of the earth (see Fig. 2) .

The source of water on Earth is the rain fall from clouds, and ALLAH Almighty has precisely determined the type of those clouds (through which clouds or clouds form in the sky of the earth, and also mentioning them of the types of these clouds categorically denies that this Qur'an is composed by humans, but rather is a house of It is a knowledgeable expert who is glorified and exalted, and it is surprising that a scientist who used the types of clouds gave one of the kinds the Qur'anic designation for this type, which is cumulus clouds where they mean accumulated or accumulated, as he mentioned the cold does not come to him clouds have extensions in the sky appear to those who see it from above as if it were Mountains, as shown by pictures taken by planes and airplanes It is also surprising that the Holy Qur'an describes some clouds as heavy and this cannot be absorbed by the general public, because clouds of all kinds fly through the air, so how can some of them be heavy and others light, but meteorologists in modern times know very well what is the meaning That the clouds are heavy, but rather they call them "heavy clouds", which are clouds loaded with large quantities of water, so they hardly fly in the air because of their weight and therefore we see them close to the surface of the earth, as it appears in the upper picture and the great truth of God who says "He who shows you Lightning is fear and covetousness and creates the cloud To Thagal (12) "Thunder.

Here, the Qur'an's description and identification of the elements of the fertility of the earth and the change of its shape from barren to green within climatic conditions and a destination that he defined to be the source of sustainability and environmental protectionism from corruption and damage emerged. We can ignore these scientific facts that are mentioned in the Book of God.

Chapter Four: Quran and Human Behavior

The Qur'an has defined social relations in its various aspects. Private and public relations are determined by that most accurate relationship. This has been proven by scientific studies that have proven the validity of this relationship. With punishment, he made paradise reward and fire as punishment and set conditions for obedience and acceptance of prayers within the frameworks of scientific knowledge indicating the greatness of the Creator in understanding the human self by saying.

(إِنَّا لَدِينِكُم مَّا نَزَّلْنَا لَكُم مَّا أَقْبَلْنَا أَوْ لِنَكُم مَّا أَكَلُوا نَفِيطُوا نَهْمًا لِنَارٍ وَلَا يَكْتُمُهُمَا اللَّهُ وَمَا لَقِيَامَتِهِ وَلَا يُزَكِّيهِمْ وَلَهُمْ عَذَابٌ أَلِيمٌ)
سورة البقرة¹⁷⁴

(يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اتَّقُوا اللَّهَ هُوَ مَنصُورٌ حَاسِرٌ بِكُمْ أَن تُكْفَرُوا عَنْكُمْ سِيئَاتِكُمْ يُدْخِلُكُمْ جَنَّاتٍ تَجْرِي مِن تَحْتِهَا الْأَنْهَارُ يَوْمَ لَا يُخِزُ بِاللَّهِ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا وَهُمْ فِيهَا
مُتَسَعِّدِينَ يُبَدِّلُهُمْ بِأَيْمَانِهِمْ يُقُولُونَ رَبَّنَا إِنَّا أَمْنَا نَارًا وَنَاوَا غَيْرَ لَنَا إِنَّا كُنَّا كُفْرًا عَقِيدِينَ)
سورة التحريم⁸

From here we can determine the time for human life, specifically Muslim man. The average life span of a Muslim in the Middle East ranges from 65-75 years. If we divide the actual rate of time, today is equal to 24 hours. That is, in the week 168, and in the month 672 hours, and in the year 8064 hours, then we find the number of hours in 75 years (604800) hours, according to statistics for individual activities see Table 1 .

Table 1 The number of hours actually used per year

Activity	Women	Men
Sleep	1752	1713
Eating	281	274
Preparing food	440	154
House Cleaning	412	117
Childcare	367	196
Social visits	395	472
Garden Care	142	182
Purchase of goods and services	234	283
Other housework	379	283
Total	4402	4402

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization.

Table 2 Activities

Activities	Women	Men
Crafts	207	120
Work and related activities	545	149
Go to work and back from work	314	328
total	1066	597

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization.

Table 3 Activities

Activities	Women	Men
Going to and from school	129	144
Always in class	737	748
Study and research	448	422
reading	322	308
total	1636	1622

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization.

Table 4 Health care and personal care

Activities	Women	Men
Healthcare	126	122
Personal care	136	124
total	262	246

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization.

Table 5 Personal activities

activities	Women	Men
Internet	95	147
Phone calls	104	112
Watching TV	583	628
Other sports and hobbies	286	417
total	1304	1068

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization.

Table 6 Cultural and religious activities

activities	Women	Men
Political activity	126	148
Religious activity	209	219
total	335	367

Source: Ministry of Planning, Central Statistical Organization

From the above, it becomes clear that the number of hours spent by men is 6245 hours per year, which represents its proportion, which is equivalent to 71%. As for the rest of the time in the year, it is a lost time between movement and eliminating needs. 8% and activities outside the home occupy 25.9%, while the proportion of health and personal care is 4.19%, and the proportion of personal activities is 20.8%, and the proportion of political and religious activities reached 5.8%, which is the lowest rate where it reached The percentage of time that he uses for his worshipper year is 3.5%.

While the total number of hours used for women reached 4,717 hours per year, this represents 56.4%, which is a very low percentage of the hours spent by men, as it makes a difference of 15%, which is a large percentage, but it varies with the percentage of hours spent for each activity where internal activities are occupied It accounted for 93.3%, the number of hours spent outside the home was 6.6%, and activities related to work outside the home 34.6%, while the number of hours consumed for health and personal services was 5.5%, secondary activities and hobbies 22.6%, political and religious activities 7.1%, as the time used to worship reached 4.4%.

Hence the great imbalance in the exploitation of time in the living environment for both sexes is revealed to reveal the causes of scientific and technical delay, which contradicts Manzel from heavenly teachings in the Holy Qur'an for Muslims.

Conclusion

The Qur'an is the constitution of mankind and he has taken care of the factor of time and its role in the environment from the social, economic and cultural aspects. It is a guide to the life, progress and optimal investment of the Islamic nation. Therefore, noble verses in daily life cannot be condoned to attain development and increase production in various aspects of life in order to reach what the nations have reached through respecting Time and achievement for each moment within a systematic framework.

Recommendations

- 1) Establishing a schedule for each accomplished and planning in advance.
- 2) Adherence to Islamic teachings through the guidance of the Holy Quran and the noble hadiths of the time.
- 3) Highlighting the role of women in various human activities to create an educated generation eager to use time.
- 4) Addressing and mitigating weaknesses and preventing minimizing the economic and social impacts imposed by the environmental reality.
- 5) Sincerity in work and giving the appropriate time for every human activity that desires. Time does not depart from human life as black.

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